

Self-Leadership: A Theological Approach

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ABSTRACT: It is not a secret that the leader is the strategic person in a community. But what is the one secret of a leader that really make a difference for the society? The thesis of this article is that the self-leadership is one of the important keys to personal development and to the development of a society. This paper surveys the self-leadership quality of the spiritual leaders, and focuses on the particular ingredients of self-leadership as described by Apostle Paul in the New Testament.

KEY WORDS: self-leadership, character, family, community.

Every person should be a leader. Even somebody is not in a position of a leader or hold an office as leader he must lead himself. There are so many decisions to be made every single day and so many targets to be reached and everyone needs wisdom, determination and action. So, self-leadership is a must have quality of every person.

This is even more so for visible leaders, the one who have responsibility to move others toward a better future. By definition a leader is the one who go before others, show the way, pave the way, lead the way and live the way. For this reason the self-leadership for leaders is so critical. Real leadership, when people follow out of respect, is impossible if the self-leadership is absent in the life of a leader.

Even it is obvious, it is important to ask whether or not is biblical to speak about leadership, especially in churches. Does God, through the Bible say anything about leading? Also in the postmodern society, we may ask if somebody has the right to tell others what to do? This challenge is real because “in the age of pragmatism in the secular world, where the ends justify the means, the temptation is for leadership to prostitute Christian character for the sake of success. Moreover, in a culture that increasingly extols success at any cost and puts down virtues as a worthy goal, leaders may unwittingly pursue the glitter of success and lose the joy of serving Christ.”¹ To responding to this situation and to answer this question is very important for this thesis. Alex D. Montoya presented four biblical guidelines in this regard:

- The entire history of God’s dealings with His people is actually God’s involvement with a particular person whom He uses to accomplish His will. When God wanted to accomplish something, He was looking for a person to lead His people;
- The New Testament spells out in clear terms that God has a designated leadership for His church. The apostles were the first designated leaders (Matt. 10:1–42; 18:18–20), then the elders are overseers of the congregation (Acts 14:23; 20:17; Titus 1:5; Phil. 1:1; 1 Tim. 3:1) Leading is listed among the gifts given to the church (Rom. 12:8; 1 Cor. 12:28);
- Certain charges addressed to individuals in the New Testament indicate that these men were to exercise leadership in the church. Both Paul and Peter gives clear exhortations to elders (1 Tim. 5:17–25; Titus 1:5–9; 1 Pet. 5:1–5);
- The church has received special exhortations regarding treatment of church leaders (1 Cor. 16:16, 18; 1 Thess. 5:12–13; Heb. 13:7, 17, 24.)²

In this article we will concentrate on spiritual leaders, as the highest form of leadership,³ but the principles apply very well to any kind of leader. The most condensed text in the Bible concerning self-leadership is 1 Tim. 3:1–7. David Guzik introduces this passage by saying: “Leaders are not to be chosen at random, nor just because they volunteer, nor because they aspire to the position, nor even

because they are “natural leaders.” Instead they should be chosen primarily on how they match the qualifications listed here.”⁴ Here is the biblical text:

Here is a trustworthy saying: Whoever aspires to be an overseer desires a noble task. Now the overseer is to be above reproach, faithful to his wife, temperate, self-controlled, respectable, hospitable, able to teach, not given to drunkenness, not violent but gentle, not quarrelsome, not a lover of money. He must manage his own family well and see that his children obey him, and he must do so in a manner worthy of full respect. (If anyone does not know how to manage his own family, how can he take care of God’s church?) He must not be a recent convert, or he may become conceited and fall under the same judgment as the devil. He must also have a good reputation with outsiders, so that he will not fall into disgrace and into the devil’s trap.

This passage refers to the needed qualification of a spiritual leader, either a overseer, bishop, elder, pastor, or a more general term—minister.⁵ Most of these qualifications are not about what he will do, but what he will be. Even this preoccupation was present through the centuries; the twentieth century of Christian church history has witnessed an increased emphasis upon the spiritual life of the pastor as the main spiritual leader. When Jesus called people to discipleship, He first called them *to be*, followed by *to do*. In the New Testament, especially in the texts where the pastor’s role is described, the first and most important part is the description of his character. Ministry is not a job, a way of making a living, nor a profession. These types of sentiments have been increasingly stressed in recent literature.

In the 1980s, the Leadership Network conducted a study to determine the characteristic of the pastors who are most crucial to the development of a vital congregation. The first requirement for a pastor of a congregation with 1,000+ members was: “The pastor must adhere to private spiritual disciplines, develop ‘holy habits,’ love God with a passion—he or she must live in the Scriptures, pray, love God with fidelity and integrity.”⁶ But this expectation is not only for pastors at the large churches. In 1989–90, McCormick

Theological Seminary conducted a large nationwide study to explore the expectations of congregations and judiciary executives regarding the role expectations of the pastor in congregations of all sizes. “The survey discussed and ranked twenty–one possible ministry roles. The roles are listed in rank order: personal integrity, preacher, care giver, worship leader, sense of call, interpersonal skills, personal Spiritual renewal, wisdom, spiritual guide. . . .”⁷ This survey makes clear that the first expectation for a pastor from many is his character, his integrity, and his spirituality. A pastor’s activity is a reflection of his character. Even preaching, care giving, and worshiping are ranked higher than homiletics, charity, and music by those responding to this survey.

Others think differently. Robert C Anderson, surprised by the manner in which the people enter into ministry, wrote:

During the course of each school year dozens of inquiries came across my desk regarding men who are being considered by churches. . . . Without exception, each inquires as to the abilities of the person being considered, his personality traits, and the talents of his wife. Rarely does a questionnaire deal with character traits. . . . Although the Bible often states the kind of things that elder, pastor, or overseer do, nowhere does it specify the talents we may expect in them. . . . Although they need those qualities to perform their duties, the Bible’s major emphasis is in an entirely different direction; instead of insisting on how well a person is able to perform a certain function, it focuses instead on what kind of a person he is.⁸

It becomes clear that the first question is: “Who is the pastor?” or, “What kind of person is he?” Thomas C. Oden presented two possible mistakes as far as thinking about a minister is concerned: “*reductionism*, the characteristically modern misjudgment about ministry, attempts to reduce the essence of ministry to a human social function or the philosophical insight or to moral teaching or to psychological counseling or to political change advocacy. (Failure to understand divine commission) . . . and *triumphalism*, a habit more characteristic of pre–modern consciousness. It loses track of the human, finite side of ministry in the interest of inordinately stressing its divine origin and eternal purpose.”⁹ The pastor is not a divine

being, and at the same time, is not a person who decides by himself to become a minister. A balanced definition of the pastor could be: “he [the pastor] is an ordinary person who knows the Lord Jesus Christ as a personal Savior, has experienced the call of God in his life for full-time Christian service, and knows that he is fit for such service because he meets certain biblical character qualifications.”¹⁰ In other words, the pastor is a saved, called and qualified person.

Above Reproach

This quality is seen as essential by many for a modern pastor. John MacArthur said: “There, the single, overarching qualification of which the rest are supportive is that he is to be ‘above reproach’. That is, he must be a leader who cannot be accused of anything sinful. All the other qualifications, except perhaps teaching and management skill, only amplify that idea.”¹¹ “It is common for employers,” said Edwing Louis Cole, “to be impressed with man of charisma, talent, ability, and as a result, commit some aspects of management or church life to the man. Then they suffer the chaos and loss from his unfaithful practice. Faithfulness is the cornerstone of character.”¹² Gardiner Spring, in his chapter “The Personal Piety of a minister,” lets us see his concern about the subject and his disappointment concerning the way this subject is received. “There is no topic on which the writer addresses his brethren in the ministry, either young or old, with more reluctance and shamefacedness, than that which is here indicated. ... True piety is its own evidence wherever it exists in the soul.”¹³ James Stalker presented that the purpose of a minister in a parish “is not to cultivate scholarship, or to visit the people during the week, but it is to live among them as a good man, whose mere presence is a demonstration which cannot be gainsaid that there is a life possible on earth which is fed from no earthly source, and that the things spoken of in the church on Sabbath are realities.”¹⁴ This standard is very high, but not too high with the help of God. When we look at the areas in which the pastor should work, we find that he is supposed to pass three tests: (1) the test at home, (2) the test in the church, and (3) the test outside the church, in the society.

The Husband of *One* Wife

The spirit of this text is not saying that a pastor must be married. To be married is not a spiritual qualification. God is saying something even more than just that a pastor should have a monogamous marriage. Lynn Anderson noted that in the family, the leader's true character comes through. Being the husband of one wife means first of all moral purity and fidelity of thoughts and actions. The positive part is that the husband is a lover and makes the wife feel securely cherished and valued. They have a healthy intimate relationship and are happy together. The husband demonstrates by the stability of his marriage that he can keep covenants.¹⁵ Concerning being pure, Robert Anderson said that the pastor "should avoid the things that corrupt the mind and erode conscience. He should be careful not to view films or television indiscriminately, and under no circumstances should he feed the prurient recesses of his mind with pornography."¹⁶ David Guzik is very explicit when he points: "The idea is that is love and affection and heart is given to one woman, and that being his lawful and wedded wife. This means that the Biblical leader is not a playboy, an adulterer, a flirt, and does not show romantic or sexual interest in other women, including the depictions or images of women in pornography."¹⁷ The idea of purity is to be held even if a pastor is not married yet, purity not only of the body, but also of his heart, mind, and eyes.

"Managing his own household well" is a big umbrella over the activities at home. The pastor has to keep his children under control with dignity. He is to gain the respect of his children. "If an elder cannot inspire the love and respect of his adult children, why should he expect the love and respect of the church?"¹⁸ His wife plays an important role in this. They are supposed to be a team and work together and be an example of loving discipline. Surely the kids are not to be perfect, but they should not be accused of dissipation or rebellion.

"Hospitable," that love of strangers or guests, is the key that opens the house for others. Spiritual relationship with others deepens best as people are gathered in each other's homes. This

does not mean to have a lack of privacy. Rather, it means to offer an example for the church members to follow.

“Temperate” holds the idea of being strong and self-controlled, especially in the area of appetites. The key thought here is moderation. No excesses are commendable, even in his work.

“Prudent” has a connotation of sensibility. He will not do certain things that will offend others. “He is not loud or rude or boisterous in places and situations where such behavior is not considered acceptable. He does not flaunt a ‘macho’ image to convey exaggerated images . . . he is not overly competitive in his activities.”¹⁹

“Respectable,” or of a good behavior, holds the idea of orderliness of personality, modesty and decorum. There is no room for vulgarity of speech, offensive actions, or any indecent dress.

“Able to teach” is not necessarily a gift of teaching. Rather, it means to be ‘at home’ in the Bible, and to know how to teach, advise, and correct. It indicates a person who loves the Bible, reads the Bible, memorizes the Bible, and lives the Bible. The pastor should be morally qualified to teach before he should be a gifted speaker. It is also a matter of being pleasant and having a good reputation so that the people will love to hear him or ask his opinion on a certain issue.

“Not addicted to wine” is a matter of controlling the appetites, an idea larger than only wine. Lynn Anderson notices that some Christians consider that they have the freedom to drink without becoming addicted. “But let us say emphatically that people who are obsessed with looking for freedoms, especially those freedoms that could jeopardize the call of God, are not people with a heart for God!”²⁰ They are slaves of their freedom.

“Not Pugnacious” means to avoid fights and to control the temper. The leader is not to be easy provoked, and, by no means, to hurt somebody in any way. Close to this qualification is “uncontentious.” The pastor is not “to glory in a good argument,”²¹ not to devastate opponents with words.

“Free from the love of money” is also an issue of control. The pastor should control the money, not let the money control him. He “wants no part in ‘ill-gotten gain’.” He makes sure that his money is earned fairly and honestly.”²² Money are deceitful because they promise a security and happiness they cannot offer. The most

precious goods in life cannot be obtained with money: health, knowledge, peace, forgiveness, joy...!

“Not self-willed” is a restriction against arrogance and selfishness. A pastor is not to be concerned about his satisfaction nor the accomplishments of his goals. An opposite of this bad trait is humbleness. To be humble means to accept the will of God gladly and to understand that God is in control. “A humble spirit is the hallmark of the man God uses.”²³

“Self controlled” is the last fruit of the Spirit. This characteristic is also very broad. Many other qualifications can stay under this umbrella. “The person who by the help of the Holy Spirit can control himself certainly will have no problem succeeding in any task that God had in mind for him to do.”²⁴

A pastor is to have a “good reputation with those outside the church.” This means that he is to be a good neighbor who demonstrates the love of God to them. How is he known among his business colleagues? How does he treat people outside the church? The pastor represents the church in the society. The expectations of people are big concerning a spiritual Christian leader. Bob Russell implies the fact that purity is not only for the ministry in the church, but outside the church. “When we fail to live lives of purity, the world mocks.”²⁵

All these qualifications, presented in the three tests, describe what a pastor should be in order to start doing ministry. If these are passed successfully, there is a great chance to have a wonderful church with excellent leadership. But what are the functions of the pastor? Even the most spiritual pastor is of no help if he does nothing. So, what is a pastor supposed to do?

In conclusion, we have found that the character of the spiritual leader is the highest priority. He is a person with a calling from God and with a godly character. Above reproach is the main and all-inclusive characteristic of a pastor. He must be a self-leader being an example of a faithful and loving father and husband, managing his own house, being an example of character and spiritual wisdom, and having a good reputation among the people from outside the church. Only in this way, a spiritual leader is a role model for self-leadership, which is so needed in our society today!

NOTES

¹ Cf. Alex D. Montoya, "Leading," in MacArthur, Jr. John, et al. *Rediscovering Pastoral Ministry, Shaping Contemporary Ministry with Biblical Mandates*, (Dallas: World Publishing, 1995), 286–87.

² Montoya, *Leading*, 285.

³ We called spiritual leadership as a highest form of leadership, because, in spiritual contexts leaders can not use any means of urging people to follow or take action. They have only the power of their character and example. People follow because they want, not because they have to!

⁴ Cf. https://www.blueletterbible.org/comm/guzik_david/studyguide_1ti/1ti_3.cfm (Last accessed: November 10, 2016)

⁵ I will use the term "pastor" as the inclusive term for any type of spiritual leaders.

⁶ Norman Shawchuck, *Leading the Congregation* (Abington: Roger Henser, 1993), 115.

⁷ Shawchuck, 116.

⁸ Robert C. Anderson, *The Effective Pastor, A Practical Guide to the Ministry* (Chicago: Moody Press, 1985), 3–4.

⁹ Thomas C. Oden, *Pastoral Theology, Essentials of ministry* (San Francisco: Harper & Row Publishers, 1983), 55.

¹⁰ Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 4.

¹¹ John MacArthur, Jr., *Answering the Key questions about Elders*, (Panorama City, CA: Grace to you, 1988), 14.

¹² Edwin Louis Cole, *On becoming a real Man* (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1992), 86.

¹³ Gardiner Spring, *The Power of the Pulpit, Thoughts addressed to Christians Ministers and those who hear them* (Edinburgh: The Banner of Truth Trust, 1986), 145–47.

¹⁴ James Stalker, "The Preacher and His Models," in Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 4

¹⁵ Lynn Anderson, *They Smell like Sheep, Spiritual Leadership for the 21st Century* (West Monroe, Louisiana: Howard Publishing, 1997), 144–46.

¹⁶ Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 6.

¹⁷ Cf. https://www.blueletterbible.org/comm/guzik_david/studyguide_1ti/1ti_3.cfm (Last accessed: November 16, 2016)

¹⁸ Anderson, *They Smell like Sheep*, 149.

¹⁹ Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 7.

²⁰ Anderson, *They Smell like Sheep*, 162.

²¹ Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 12.

²² Anderson, *They Smell like Sheep*, 161.

²³ LeRoy Eims, *Be the Leader you were meant to be, Biblical Principles for leadership* (Wheaton IL: Victor Books Publishing, 1975), 31.

²⁴ Anderson, *The Effective Pastor*, 19.

²⁵ Bob Russell, *When God builds a Church, 10 principles for Growing a Dynamic Church* (West Monroe, Louisiana: Howard Books, 2000), 76.